

FILIPINO PRESERVICE MATHEMATICS TEACHERS' MATHEMATICAL VALUES

Rommel O. Gregorio ¹, John Louie S. Marasigan ²

¹*Philippine Science High School-Central Luzon Campus in Clark Freeport Zone, Philippines*

²*Laguna State Polytechnic University-Siniloan Campus, Laguna, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17735047>

ABSTRACT

This study examines the mathematical values of Filipino preservice mathematics teachers in relation to their sex, year level, and the type of senior high school they attended, using a quantitative design. Seventy preservice secondary mathematics teachers from a state university in the Philippines were surveyed. Data were collected using a five-point Likert-type scale developed by Durmus and Bicak (2006) and analyzed using descriptive statistics and nonparametric tests. Results showed that preservice mathematics teachers predominantly hold constructivist values. The mathematical values of preservice teachers do not differ significantly by sex or by the type of senior high school they attended. A significant difference was observed by year level, with upper-year preservice teachers tending to adopt stronger constructivist values than first-year preservice teachers. Positivist values still persist among the preservice teachers, indicating integration of the two mathematical values. These results highlight the effectiveness of teacher education programs in promoting constructivist values and promoting equitable learning experiences among the preservice teachers.

Keywords: *preservice mathematics teachers, mathematical values, positivist values, constructivist values*

INTRODUCTION

Values serve as a moral compass, shaping human behavior and interactions within society. They represent ethical standards, social responsibilities, and cultural ideals that

inform daily decisions and relationships (Tripura, 2025). Schools and educators play a critical role in fostering these values, supporting students' moral and intellectual development (Tripura, 2025).

Several studies have revealed that preservice teachers often form mathematical values and beliefs from their own experiences, and those values and beliefs strongly influence their teaching practices, classroom behavior, and views of mathematics as a discipline. Values and beliefs, as internal perspectives, guide mathematics teachers in decisions and actions that reflect their values (Bishop et al., 2003). Teachers' values and beliefs regarding mathematics can influence their classroom behavior, particularly the types of questions posed, the depth of inquiry, and the extent of methodological guidance (Kajander, 2004; McDougall et al., 2000, as cited in Kajander, 2007). Preservice teachers often develop their mathematical beliefs long before entering teacher education, and these beliefs are usually "resistant to change" (Shilling, 2010). Understanding these beliefs helps teacher education programs create curriculum materials and help the teacher educators influence preservice teachers' mathematical beliefs (Shilling, 2010).

In mathematics education, two predominant values are positivist and constructivist. Positivist values are commonly observed in teacher-centered classrooms, where the teacher is regarded as the primary source of knowledge. This perspective aligns with the "schema view" of mathematics described by Grigutsch et al. (1998, as cited in Weber, 2025), in which mathematics is understood as a set of procedures, definitions, rules, and formulas applied to solve a well-defined problem.

On the other hand, constructivist values give importance on active student engagement, where the learners are at the center of the learning process and construct their own knowledge and understanding through exploration, reflection, and interaction. Kusuma et al. (2021) emphasized that in constructivism, learning is conceptualized as the construction of knowledge through interactions with objects, phenomena, experiences, and environment, with teachers serving as moderators or facilitators who guide and support the development of deeper mathematical reasoning. Moreover, Simon (1995) presented that constructivist principles can guide classroom decision-making by helping teachers balance instructional objectives with careful attention to students' mathematical thinking.

In 2006, Durmus and Bicak developed a scale to categorize mathematical values into constructivist and positivist. They found that preservice teachers consistently scored higher on constructivist values, regardless of gender or department (mathematics education, science education, and elementary department). This was supported by Dede (2009), where both elementary and secondary Turkish preservice mathematics teachers lean towards constructivist values over positivist values in mathematics teaching.

Literature provides limited insights exploring the relationship between demographic factors and preservice teachers' mathematical values and attitudes. In their paper, Yildiz et al. (2020) found that male pre-service teachers have more positive attitudes for courses in mathematics than female pre-service teachers, but the difference

was not statistically significant. According to Fadlilmula et al. (2013) there is a notable shift in preservice teachers' attitudes towards teaching across various year levels, indicating a decline in attitudes from lower to higher levels. Moreover, they found out that female preservice teachers demonstrated more positive attitudes than their male counterparts.

In 2024, Ignacio conducted a qualitative study exploring the beliefs of Filipino preservice mathematics teachers using methods such as metaphor construction, drawing tasks, and unstructured interviews. There were four distinct belief themes identified: the teacher as a knowledge dispenser, the teacher as a reliable improver, the teachers as an equity promoter, and the teacher as a strategic scaffolder. These findings provide significant insights into preservice teachers' perceptions of their roles and responsibilities in the mathematics classroom, highlighting the diversity and complexity of their instructional beliefs.

Building on Durmus and Bicak's (2006) scale, this study adopts a quantitative-descriptive approach. It investigates the mathematical values of Filipino preservice mathematics teachers. Specifically, it analyzes the types of mathematical values (positivist and constructivist) held by Filipino preservice mathematics teachers, by sex, year level, and type of senior high school. It also examines how these values vary across demographics. Using quantitative methods, the study aims to clarify the relationship between demographic factors and mathematical values of Filipino preservice mathematics teachers. Overall, it contributes to the literature on mathematics education in the Philippines.

Research Questions

The primary aim of this study was to examine the mathematical values (positivist values and constructivist values) of Filipino preservice mathematics teachers. In particular, it sought to answer the following questions about the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers from Z University:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1 Sex
 - 1.2 Year Level
 - 1.3 School Type (in their Senior High School)
2. What are the mathematical values of the preservice mathematics teachers?
3. Are there significant differences in the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers when grouped by?
 - 3.1. Year level
 - 3.2. Sex
 - 3.3. School Type (in their Senior High School)

Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant difference in the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers when grouped by

- Sex
- Year Level
- School Type (in their Senior High School)

H₁: There is significant difference in the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers when grouped by

- Sex
- Year Level
- School Type (in their Senior High School)

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative-descriptive research design, utilizing a questionnaire to collect data on preservice teachers' mathematical values. This approach was selected for its effectiveness in gathering data on preservice teachers' personal preferences regarding the importance or worth of a thought or statement to them (Dede, 2009). The dependent variables are the mean scores on the positivist values subscale (positivist values) and the constructivist values subscale (constructivist values), while the demographic variables are sex, year level, and school type in senior high school.

Respondents

The study involved 70 preservice secondary mathematics teachers from a state university in the Philippines, which we refer to in this paper as Z University, comprising 18 males and 52 females. In the context of this study, preservice teachers are students who are currently studying to become licensed or professional teachers but have not yet begun full-time teaching. They are enrolled in a teacher education program, taking education and subject-specific courses.

During the first semester of academic year 2025-2026, only 78 students were enrolled in the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics. The computed minimum sample size was 65 respondents based on a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. However, 70 respondents were included in the study to account for potential non-response and to enhance the reliability of the findings. Oversampling beyond the minimum requirement is consistent with best practices in survey research, particularly in small populations.

Instrument and Data Gathering

Data were collected using a five-point Likert-type scale developed by Durmus and Bicak (2006) in Google Form version, which measures two mathematical values: positivist

and constructivist. The instrument demonstrated a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.73 overall, with 0.64 for positivist values and 0.74 for constructivist values (Durmus and Bicak, 2006). A confidentiality clause was included in the instrument to ensure the privacy of participants' responses. Submitting names was not required, and there was no request for any other personally identifiable information, including student numbers or addresses. Respondents were requested to specify their sex, year level, and type of senior high school.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) were used to summarize demographic data. To determine significant differences in preservice teachers' mathematical values according to year level, sex, and senior high school type, non-parametric tests like Wilcoxon signed-rank test, Mann-Whitney U test, and Kruskal Wallis H test were applied at a 0.05 significance level, employing SPSS 27.0 software.

RESULTS

A total of 70 preservice teachers participated in this study, comprising 18 males and 52 females. The sample included 13 first-year, 20 second-year, 19 third-year, and 18 fourth-year students. Most of the students came from public schools when they were in senior high school. All respondents were enrolled in the Bachelor of Secondary Education program major in Mathematics, during the first semester of the academic year 2025-2026.

Table 1.
Demographic profile of the respondents

Variable	Group	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	18	26%
	Female	52	74%
Year Level	First Year	13	19%
	Second Year	20	28%
	Third Year	19	27%
	Fourth Year	18	26%
Type of School in Senior High	Public	61	87%
	Private	9	13%

In the instrument developed by Durmus and Bicak (2006), the items numbered 1, 2, 3, 7, 14, 17, 19, 21, 22, 26, 28, 30, 31 and 32 are assigned to positivist values in

mathematics, while the items numbered 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 18, 20, 23, 24, 25, 27, 29, 33 and 34 are assigned to constructivist values in mathematics.

Table 2.

Summary of the survey result based on the instrument developed by Durmus and Bicak (2006)

	Items	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1	Finding the correct solution of a problem should be emphasized in mathematics teaching.	4.19	1.22	Agree
2	The straight teaching of mathematical concepts and relations is the main task of a mathematics teacher.	4.09	1.06	Agree
3	New subjects in mathematics cannot be learned without knowing previous subjects.	4.30	1.01	Strongly Agree
4	The essence of mathematics learning is to learn mathematical concepts and relations to solve routine and non-routine problems.	4.17	1.08	Agree
5	Mathematics is a thinking tool developed to fulfill people's needs.	4.06	1.06	Agree
6	Mathematics is an activity based on creativity such as art.	3.89	1.10	Agree
7	Mathematics can be understood only by people who are clever.	3.46	1.59	Agree
8	The essence of school mathematics is to develop problem-solving skills of students.	4.29	1.07	Strongly Agree
9	Mathematics is not a new invention but a whole discovered body of knowledge developed through history.	4.06	1.11	Agree
10	The process of solving a problem is as important as finding the correct solution.	4.39	1.05	Strongly Agree
11	The essence of problem solving is to prepare students to deal with problems encountered in daily life.	4.24	1.08	Strongly Agree
12	The goal of school mathematics is to develop a sense of joy and appreciation of mathematics.	4.26	1.09	Strongly Agree
13	Mathematics in essence generates practical solutions for problems.	4.16	1.11	Agree

14	Mathematical knowledge cannot be discussed.	3.43	1.53	Agree
15	In mathematics teaching, estimations on solutions should be emphasized rather than paper and pencil calculations.	3.71	0.98	Agree
16	Mathematics has a vital role in the development of civilizations.	4.13	0.99	Agree
17	Teacher-centered activities are essential in mathematics teaching.	3.91	1.07	Agree
18	The most efficient mathematics teaching is possible only when the logic behind rules and procedures is understood.	4.04	1.00	Agree
19	Students should try to understand teacher's explanations instead of making sense of mathematical concepts on their own.	3.93	0.92	Agree
20	Most jobs require mathematical thinking rather than mathematics itself.	3.90	0.87	Agree
21	The teacher is the main source of mathematical knowledge.	3.87	1.03	Agree
22	Mathematical knowledge has cultural aspects.	4.03	0.72	Agree
23	Students learn not only from their correct solution but also from their mistakes.	4.41	0.97	Strongly Agree
24	In mathematics teaching, activities should be designed so that students are actively involved.	4.17	1.10	Agree
25	The essence of mathematics teaching is to enable students to discover mathematical concepts and relations.	4.17	1.01	Agree
26	It is not proper that students are always in need of using concrete models in mathematics teaching.	3.77	0.85	Agree
27	Teachers and students should construct mathematical knowledge together.	4.30	0.91	Strongly Agree
28	In school mathematics, all students can learn basic mathematical knowledge and skills at the same level.	3.87	1.05	Agree
29	Mathematical knowledge is necessary to be successful in a profession.	3.86	0.95	Agree
30	Mathematics as an intellectual human endeavor is developed to solve its own problems.	3.94	0.96	Agree

31	There is always a certain way of solving a mathematical problem.	4.21	0.95	Strongly Agree
32	Mathematical knowledge is culture-free.	3.89	1.06	Agree
33	The essence of mathematics learning is to learn the logic behind mathematical rules and knowledge.	4.21	0.85	Strongly Agree
34	Sequence of mathematical subjects does not have an effect on learning performance.	3.89	1.39	Agree

Table 3 indicates that the mean score on the constructivist values (M=3.93, SD=0.897) is higher than the mean score on the positivist values (M=3.55, SD=0.753). The Shapiro-Wilk test revealed that the data for constructivist values were not normally distributed, $W(70)=0.214$, $p<0.001$. Consequently, a nonparametric test was employed. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test identified a significant difference between the positivist values and constructivist values ($Z=-5.411$, $p<0.001$, $r=0.65$).

Table 3.

Descriptive statistics and results of Wilcoxon signed rank test on the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers

Values	N	Mean	SD	Mean Rank	Z	p-value
Positivist	70	3.55	0.753	28.75	-5.411	<0.001
Constructivist	70	3.93	0.897	35.49		

Table 4 shows that the both mathematical values of preservice male teachers (positivist values: M=3.60, SD=0.753; constructivist values: M=4.08, SD=0.808) are higher than those of preservice female teachers (positivist values: M=3.54, SD=0.760; constructivist values: M=3.88, SD=0.928). However, Mann-Whitney U test revealed no significant difference on either positivist values (U=447, $Z=-0.282$, $p=0.778$) and constructivist values (U=395, $Z=-0.982$, $p=0.326$) of the preservice teachers when grouped by sex.

Table 4.**Descriptive statistics and results of Mann-Whitney U test on the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers when grouped by sex**

Values	Sex	N	Mean	SD	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	Z	p-value
Positivist	Male	18	3.60	0.753	36.67	660.00	447	-0.282	0.778
	Female	52	3.54	0.760	35.10	1825.00			
Constructivist	Male	18	4.08	0.808	39.56	712.00	395	-0.982	0.326
	Female	52	3.88	0.928	34.10	1773.00			

Table 5 indicates that the mean scores on the constructivist values (M=3.43, 3.86, 4.12, 4.16 from first to fourth year) are higher than those for positivist values (M=3.33, 3.66, 3.64, 3.65 from first to fourth year) across all year levels of the preservice mathematics teachers. Because the data did not meet the normality assumption according to the Shapiro-Wilk test ($p < 0.001$), the Kruskal-Wallis H test was employed. The Kruskal-Wallis H test indicated that the positivist values did not differ significantly when grouped by year level $\chi^2(3, N=70) = 6.667$, $p = 0.083$. Whereas a significant difference was found in the constructivist values when grouped by year level $\chi^2(3, N=70) = 9.470$, $p = 0.024$. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Dunn's test revealed that the constructivist values of first-year preservice teachers (mean rank=19.92) differed significantly from those of second-year (mean rank=38.03), third-year (mean rank=39.97), and fourth-year (mean rank=39.92) preservice teachers. Furthermore, the mean scores on the constructivist values increase from the first to the fourth year.

Table 5.**Descriptive statistics and results of Kruskal-Wallis H test on the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers when grouped by year level**

Values	Year Level	N	Mean	SD	Mean Rank	χ^2	df	p-value
Positivist	First Year	13	3.13	0.731	23.46	6.667	3	0.083
	Second Year	20	3.66	0.942	41.90			
	Third Year	19	3.64	0.495	37.16			
	Fourth Year	18	3.65	0.711	35.33			

Constructivist	First Year	13	3.43	0.984	19.92	9.470	3	0.024
	Second Year	20	3.86	1.134	38.03			
	Third Year	19	4.12	0.648	39.97			
	Fourth Year	18	4.16	0.635	39.22			

Table 6 indicates that preservice teachers from private senior high schools have higher mean scores on the positivist values ($M=3.72$, $SD=0.530$) compared to those from public senior high schools ($M=3.52$, $SD=0.781$). The mean scores on the constructivist values were identical for preservice teachers from both public and private schools. The results of the Mann-Whitney U test indicated no significant difference in the on both positivist values ($U=233.5$, $Z=-0.720$, $p=0.471$) and constructivist values ($U=264$, $Z=-0.184$, $p=0.845$) of the preservice teachers based on the type of senior high school attended.

Table 6.

Descriptive statistics and results of Mann-Whitney U test of the values of preservice mathematics teachers when grouped by type of senior high school

Values	Sex	N	Mean	SD	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U	Z	p-value
Positivist	Public	61	3.52	0.781	34.83	2124.50	233.5	-0.720	0.471
	Private	9	3.72	0.530	40.06	360.50			
Constructivist	Public	61	3.93	0.905	35.33	2155.00	264	-0.184	0.854
	Private	9	3.93	0.893	36.67	330.00			

DISCUSSION

The present study investigates the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers at Z University. Among the respondents, the highest percentage occurs in the sex category with female participants at 74%, while the lowest is male participants at 26%, indicating a strong female majority in the sample. In year level, the highest percentage is third year at 27% and the lowest is first year at 19%, suggesting more respondents are in the middle-to-upper years of the teacher education program. For the type of senior high school, public schools dominate with 87%, while private schools constitute only 13%, reflecting a heavy public-school representation. Overall, the majority of the respondents were female and had attended public senior high schools. This is a

common demographic for bachelor in secondary education programs in the Philippines (Generalao et al., 2022).

In Table 2, the highest weighted mean observed is approximately 4.41 for item 23, “Students learn not only from their correct solution but also from their mistakes”. This item also carries a strong, near-consensus verbal interpretation of “Strongly Agree”. The relatively low standard deviation for this item reinforces the idea that this stance is widely shared among respondents. Conversely, several items cluster around mid-range means (roughly 3.4–3.9), reflecting moderate or nuanced beliefs about certain aspects of mathematics. Examples of these mid-range results include statements about cultural or social dimensions of mathematics. This has important implications for teacher education; programs may continue to emphasize explicit modeling, guided inquiry, and scaffolding while also deliberately addressing sociocultural perspectives, multiple representations, and opportunities for students to form and explain their own ideas and thinking. By integrating reflective practices, sociocultural explorations, and opportunities for students to discuss diverse mathematical concepts, programs can help preservice teachers develop a balanced orientation that combines effective teacher guidance with student autonomy and culturally responsive pedagogy.

Moreover, results also indicated that preservice mathematics teachers generally lean towards constructivist values rather than positivist ones. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test confirmed a statistically significant difference between the two mathematical values as scored by the preservice teachers. This suggests that the preservice teachers prefer learner-centered values, in which students are actively involved in generating practical solutions to problems and in discovering mathematical concepts and relations. Constructivist values also support that mathematics should develop problem-solving skills rather than focusing on pen-and-paper calculations. Additionally, the preservice teachers subscribe to the process of solving and understanding the logic behind rules and procedures rather than on the final answer alone. These results are consistent with the studies by Durmus and Bicak (2006) and Dede (2009), which found that preservice teachers tend to adopt constructivist values than positivist values. This preference may reflect the prevailing pedagogical paradigm in Philippine education, which prioritizes active and experiential learning (Saldivar, 2025). And since the preservice teachers hold constructivist values, this may shape their future teaching practices.

When grouped by sex, both male and female preservice teachers showed a stronger preference for constructivist values. Males had slightly higher mean scores on both mathematical values than the females, but the Mann-Whitney U test indicated that these differences were not statistically significant. This means that the male and female preservice teachers’ mathematical values do not differ significantly in their mathematical values. The absence of a significant difference in the present study may suggest that the teacher education program at Z University provides similar instruction, training, activities, and experiences to both male and female students. As a result, both male and female preservice teachers appear to develop similar mathematical values. Dede (2009) also found that the main effect of sex was insignificant with small effect size. However, Durmus

and Bicak (2006) identified a significant difference in the positivist values of preservice teachers, reporting that male participants demonstrated a higher mean score.

Mathematical values of preservice teachers across year levels yielded notable findings. Preservice teachers across all year levels tend to adopt constructivist values rather than positivist values. The Kruskal–Wallis H test indicated a significant overall difference on the constructivist values among preservice teachers based on their year levels. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons revealed that the constructivist values of first-year preservice teachers differed significantly from upper-year students (second-, third-, and fourth-year). However, no significant differences were observed among second-year, third-year, and fourth-year preservice teachers. These results suggest that as the preservice teachers advance through the teacher education program, they have more internalization of learner-centered perspectives on mathematics in teaching and learning. Contributing factors may include exposure to educational theories, pedagogical and content knowledge, practical teaching experiences, and field studies as the preservice teachers advance through the teacher education program. Additionally, positivist values did not significantly differ across year levels. This finding may indicate that procedural and traditional mathematical practices and values still persist with the preservice teachers, but may be gradually integrated with constructivist values rather than being entirely replaced. This aligns with Dede (2009), who found that both senior and freshman preservice teachers held constructivist values, although freshman preservice teachers scored significantly higher in positivist values than their senior counterparts.

Finally, comparing the mathematical values of preservice teachers based on the type of senior high school attended revealed no significant differences. Although students from private schools exhibited slightly higher positivist values, this difference was not significant. Moreover, both groups had almost identical constructivist values. These results indicate that the type of senior high school attended has no significant effect on their mathematical values once students enter the teacher education program. The teacher education program's focus on student-centered learning may help preservice teachers to have an equal footing at the university, thereby shaping their mathematical values. By mitigating gaps in prior schooling, such as the type of senior high school, the teacher education program contributes to broader equity goals in Philippine education, underscoring the importance of equitable teaching approaches.

Conclusions

This study explores the mathematical values of preservice mathematics teachers at Z University, revealing a predominantly female sample (74%) and strong representation from public senior high schools (87%), aligning with typical demographics in Philippine secondary education programs. This study concludes the following: first, preservice mathematics teachers predominantly hold constructivist values. This may imply that the preservice teachers have a strong orientation toward learner-centered and inquiry-based approaches. Second, the mathematical values of the preservice teachers do not differ significantly by sex. This may indicate that teacher education programs provide comparable experiences for both male and female students. Third, there is a

significant difference in mathematical values across year levels, with upper-year preservice teachers showing greater internalization of constructivist values. This suggests that progression through the teacher education program strengthens the constructivist values of the preservice teachers. Finally, the type of senior high school does not give a significant difference in the mathematical values of the preservice teachers. This underscores the teacher education program's capacity to promote equity and provide a common pedagogical foundation to the preservice teachers regardless of prior schooling.

The practical implication of these results is that teacher education programs might focus on year-level differences, exploring how curriculum exposure, field experiences, and reflective tasks across cohorts shape mathematical values, while consistently addressing other factors (sex, school type) that did not show significant effects in this study.

Overall, the findings underscore the effectiveness of the teacher education program at Z University in promoting constructivist values, supporting the development of future mathematics educators. It is also important to note that, although the preservice teachers subscribe to constructivist values, they do not abandon their positivist values. This is very important because, as Kirschner et al. (2006) reminded us, good teaching is not about choosing between traditional and progressive methods, but about knowing when and how to apply each. Guided instruction builds the essential cognitive structures that make later inquiry meaningful. When combined thoughtfully, both mathematical values can nurture preservice mathematics teachers not only to understand core principles but also to think, question, and act like true mathematicians.

Recommendations

This study has some limitations. First, collecting data from only one university means the results may not apply to other teacher education programs in the Philippines. Second, the small sample size may reduce the ability to find subtle differences based on gender, year level, or high school background. Third, because the study used a cross-sectional design, it only shows perceptions at one point in time and cannot track changes in mathematical values as preservice teachers progress through the teacher education program. Hence, it is recommended that future research should use larger and more varied samples, as well as longitudinal designs that include qualitative methods.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study complied with established ethical guidelines and standards for educational studies. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents to ensure voluntary participation and the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time. A confidentiality clause was included in the instrument to protect the privacy of the respondents' responses. Names and other personally identifiable information, such as student numbers or addresses, were not requested. The study maintained integrity by using the collected data exclusively for research purposes and by ensuring that no harm

was caused to respondents. Approval to conduct the study was obtained from the dean of the College of Education at Z University prior to data collection. There was no bias in the interpretation of the data, and the results were used purely for research. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and Grammarly was used in some parts of the paper to improve grammar and sentence structure. The researchers also declare no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study.

Acknowledgements

The researchers extend sincere gratitude to the university for permitting data collection among its students and to the respondents for their valuable time in completing the survey. The support and participation of all involved were essential to the completion of this research.

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